

Association Between Eating Behaviors and Body Mass Index in Secondary School Students of Benghazi, Libya

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Abstract

Background: Obesity is a chronic complex disease defined by extreme fat deposits that can impair health. It is commonly known that obesity is a multicausal disease, and eating behaviours is just one of the reasons. Eating behaviours is a comprehensive term that includes food choice and motives, feeding practices, dieting, and eating-related complications. The objective of this study First, to examine the relationships between age, BMI and eating behaviours. Second, to identify whether sex and BMI can influence these relationships.

Methodology: This study was conducted on 393 students of Benghazi secondary school, eating behaviours were measured using the three-factor questionnaire R18 (TEFQ18); Anthropometric measurements were measured and BMI was calculated.

Results: Outcome of this study showed no relationships between age and eating behaviours, a strong positive relationship between BMI and cognitive restraint ($r = 0.133^{**}$, $p = 0.008$) and positive relationship between BMI and emotional eating ($r = 0.119^*$, $p = 0.018$) for the whole sample. But when split the sample by sex, the relationships were significant only in females; The study also found a negative relationship between BMI and uncontrolled eating in obese people group ($r = -0.291^*$, $p = 0.033$).

Conclusion: The study found a strong positive relationship between BMI and eating behaviours in females only. The data also showed a strong negative relationship between BMI and uncontrolled eating in obese people group. These findings could help health professional and dietitian when designing strategies for obesity prevention in communities, which according to our results, should consider that, BMI, sex and eating behaviours as important factors in body weight and obesity.

Keywords: *Eating behavior, BMI, Secondary school student, Food intake, Obesity.*

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Introduction

Eating behavior is a comprehensive term that includes food choice and motives, feeding practices, dieting, and eating-related complications such as obesity, eating disorders, and feeding disorders. Inside the context of behavioral medicine, eating behavior study focuses on the etiology, prevention, and treatment of obesity and eating disorders, as well as the promotion of healthy

eating patterns that help manage and prevent medical conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and certain cancers (Gellman, 2020).

Eating behavior is a complex interplay of physiological, psychological, social, and genetic factors that impact meal timing, amount of food intake, food preference, and food selection. Active research involving the genetics of taste, food preference, pathological eating behaviors, meal size, and meal selection is rapidly growing our understanding of how and why we eat (Grimm, & Steinle, 2011). A number of research questionnaires are used to measure eating behaviors traits. One of the most commonly used is the Three-Factor Eating Questionnaire (TFEQ). R18 (TFEQ-R18), representing three revised sub-scales: Uncontrolled Eating, Emotional Eating, and Cognitive Restraint (Karlsson, et al., 2000). UE refers to a tendency to overeat, with the feeling of being out of control. EE reflects a propensity to overeat in response to negative emotions (i.e., when feeling lonely, anxious or depressed) (Karlsson, et al., 2000). CR refers to a tendency to consciously restrict food intake instead of using physiological cues (i.e., hunger and satiety) as regulators of intake (Hays, & Roberts, 2008).

Cognitive restraint over eating implies attempts to resist from eating by conscious determination in order to control body weight. The concept of dietary restraint has been considered problematic (Abdella, et al., 2023), as the restraint may pose a risk for eventual cravings and overeating (Stunkard, & Messick, 1985; Tuschl, 1990). Restraint has been associated with higher (Provencher, et al., 2003; Carbonneau, et al., 2020) but also lower body weights (Boschi, et al., 2001), and lower amount of food intake (Lindroos, et al., 1997) restraint also tends to increase with successful weight loss in overweight patients (Abdella, et al., 2023; Clark, et al., 1994). Several studies found positive relationship between restrained eating and body weight among adolescents (de Lauzon, et al., 2004) and children (Vogels, et al., 2006).

Uncontrolled Eating", defined as the tendency to lose control and overeat (Eat more than needed). Despite overeating being normal when confined to some particular occasions, it may start to become dysfunctional when it occurs regularly, despite the individual efforts to resist and the several attempts to make healthier food choices (Rossi, et al., 2022). Individuals with several episodes of overeating report the continuous feeling of being out of control choices and this sensation is also common to patients with various eating disorders, such as BN and BED, as well as obesity (Oomen, et al., 2018) - that does to date affects more than 600 million people worldwide (Liu, et al., 2023), and it is associated with several physical and psychological conditions (Al Jaber, et al., 2021).

Several studies support the idea that there is a relationship between eating, emotions and the increased energy intake (Wardle, et al., 2000; Oliver, Wardle, & Gibson, 2000). Emotional eating has been associated with greater adiposity and higher Body Mass Index (BMI) (Shriver, et al., 2019; van Strien, et al., 2016). Emotional eating has also been linked to behaviors that may contribute to increased risk of obesity overtime, including binge eating and loss of control over eating (Goossens, et al., 2009; Katterman, et al., 2014). Emotional eating has a positive relationship with rise in weight gain over time and struggle of losing weight. These can be attributed to the fact that emotional eaters are more prone to greater consumption of sugary and high-fat foods, eat in response to stressors, and snack more regularly compared to non-emotional eaters (Braden, et al., 2018).

Methodology

Study Design and Subjects

A cross-sectional study on Libyan secondary schools' students in Benghazi city. The study was applied during the period between January 2024 to May 2024. This study was approved from

research and studies department of the university of Benghazi. A list of names of government schools was obtained from the office of the director of general education in the ministry of education of Benghazi. There are 27 secondary schools for girls and 19 for boys. a sample size of 385 students was determined for the study. A multistage stratified sampling process was used. In the first stage, schools were randomly selected from a sampling frame that included all Libyan secondary schools in Benghazi city. That frame was stratified by sex; boys and girl's schools (2 strata) five schools from each division were randomly selected, i.e. 10 schools in total. One class from each grade (1st, 2nd and 3rd grades) in the selected schools was randomly chosen. Students from each class were selected randomly from the attendance lists and equally between grades. The students were interviewed, they were given a brief description about the study, its purposes, its eventual aims, and questionnaire filling way. Each of the students was given a copy from the questionnaire to fill. The questionnaire was revised for missing information or ambiguity. Unfinished or unclear questionnaires were excluded from the study. The data were anonymized and were disaggregated from information that could identify the subject. The sample of 393 students (209 males, and 184 females), The age of ranged from 15 to 18 years, (mean age + SD 17 ± 0.83 years) were included in the study.

Anthropometric Measurements

Anthropomorphic measurements for all students included in this study were measured as follows:

Height: Height was measured using a measuring tape. Participants were asked to stand tall with shoulder flat against the wall, a flat object (a book) was used to make firm contact with the top of the participant's head. A mark under the object (the book) where it lands was creating, after that a tape measure was used to determine the height from the floor to the mark. then the height was recorded to the nearest 0.1 cm.

Weight: Weight was measured to the nearest 0.1 kg using a digital scale. Subjects wore light clothing, removed their shoes and jewelers and were told to remove anything from their pockets while being weighed.

Body Mass Index (BMI): Body mass index was measured by BMI calculator for children and teenagers. It is based on the cut-off points of CDC value as mentioned before in literature (Messiah, et al., 2011). This calculator measures body mass index (BMI), which is a measure of body fat. It is only an approximate measure of the best weight for the health. As children grow, their amount of body fat changes and so will their BMI. That's why a BMI calculation for a child or adolescent must take into account their age and gender (it does this using percentile charts).

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was divided into two subsections. The first section covered various characteristics like preliminary information like gender and age. The second section was the three-factor questionnaire R 18 questions (TEFQ18).

The Three-Factor Eating Questionnaire R 18

Eating behaviors were measured using the three-factor questionnaire R18 (TEFQ18). TEFQ18 is shortened version of the original 51 item TFEQ (Stunkard, & Messick, 1985). The questionnaire measures three different aspects of eating behaviors: (a) restrained eating (b) uncontrolled eating and (c) emotional eating. The questionnaire comprises of 18 items that are measured on a 4-point response scale (definitely true: 4, mostly true: 3, mostly false: 2, definitely false: 1) and items scores are summated into subscale scores: CR, UE and EE. Restraint of cognitive by 6 items Emotional eating by 3 items and Uncontrolled eating by 9 items or questions in each category, the highest score in one of these domains prescribes the behavior when eating.

Statistical Analysis

The statistics package for the social Science (SPSS Software version (25), IBM was used for the statistical analysis with significance accepted if $p < 0.05$. Factor analysis (Pearson correlation) was applied to measure the strength and direction of association between the age and each of the three factors CR, EE, and UE and between the BMI and each of the three factors CR, EE, and UE. The graph was created by scatter plots. scatter plots are used to observe relationships among variables.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the primary variables for the overall sample and by sex are shown in table 1), The table shows that sample consisted of 393 students (mean age + SD 17 ± 0.83 years) with 53.20 % boys ($n = 209$) and 46.80 % girls ($n = 184$). The results found that there no significant differences between male and female in BMI, emotional eating and uncontrolled eating. The statistical analysis with significance accepted if $p < 0.05$.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Primary Variables for Overall Sample, by Gender

Variables	Total Mean \pm SD (n =393)	Male Mean \pm SD (n= 209)	Female Mean \pm SD (n= 184)
Age	17 ± 0.83	17 ± 0.78	17 ± 0.82
BMI	24.04 ± 6.38	23.9 ± 7.1	24.09 ± 5.3
Cognitive Restraint	13.4 ± 2.68	13.4 ± 2.7	13.41 ± 2.65
Emotional Eating	6.5 ± 2.1	6.6 ± 2.0	6.41 ± 2.21
Uncontrolled Eating	19.63 ± 3.73	19.5 ± 3.89	19.7 ± 4.01

The BMI Values of Total Sample by Gender

The BMI values of total sample and by gender categorized in the Table (2). Figure (1) shows distribution the sample by their BMI 55% of the sample had normal weight, 18.3% were overweight, 13.7% obese and 13% underweight. Table (4.2) observes that the percentages of participants who were underweight were higher in males (16.7%) compared to females (8.7%), percentages of the participants who were having normal weight were higher in females (58.7%) while in males (51.7%). The results also show no different in percentage of overweight and obese between males and females. Figure 1 shows Distribution of the sample by BMI.

Table2 The BMI Values of Total Sample and by Gender

BMI Level	N (%)	Male N (%)	Female N (%)
Under weight	51 (13%)	35 (16.7%)	16 (8.7%)
Normal weight	216 (55%)	108 (51.7%)	108 (58.7%)
Over weight	72 (18.3%)	36 (17.2%)	36 (19.6%)
Obese	54 (13.7%)	30 (14.4%)	24 (13%)
Total	393 (100%)	209	184

Figure 1. Distribution of the Sample by BMI

Relationships between Age and Eating Behaviors

Correlations between age and eating behaviors have been calculated and categorized for the overall population and by gender in tables (3). The table shows no significant relationships between age and eating behaviors.

Table 3. Relationships between Age and Eating Behaviors

Eating Behaviors	AGE		
	Total (n= 393)	Male (n= 209)	Female (n= 184)
Cognitive Restraint	r= - 0.003 p = 0.959	r = 0.054 p = 0.434	r = - 0.065 p = 0.382
Emotional Eating	r = - 0.065 p = 0.199	r = 0.045 p = 0.522	r = - 0.063 p = 0.397
Uncontrolled Eating	r = - 0.006 p = 0.907	r = 0.061 p = 0.379	r = 0.051 p = 0.492

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Relationships between BMI and Eating Behaviors

Correlations between BMI and eating behaviors have been calculated and categorized for the overall population and by gender in table (4). Table (4) shows that there is a positive significant relationship between BMI and cognitive restraint ($r = 0.133^{**}$) and between BMI and emotional eating ($r = 0.119^*$) for the whole sample. The result shows that in females there is a positive significant relationship between BMI and Cognitive Restraint ($r = 0.176^*$), also there was a positive significant relationship between BMI and Emotional Eating ($r = 0.243^{**}$), and between BMI and Uncontrolled Eating ($r = 0.207^{**}$). while there were no relationships between BMI and eating behaviors in males.

Table 4. Relationships between BMI and Eating Behaviors

Eating Behaviors	BMI		
	Total (n= 393)	Male (n= 209)	Female (n= 184)
Cognitive Restraint	r = 0.133** P = 0.008	r= 0.107 P= 0.123	r= 0.176* P = 0.017
Emotional Eating	r = 0.119* P = 0.018	r = 0.056 P = 0.417	r = 0.243** P = 0.001
Uncontrolled Eating	r = 0.089 P = 0.079	r = 0.000 P= 1.000	r = 0.207** P = 0.005

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figures (2,3&4) show the relationships between BMI and eating behaviors splitting the population by their gender, the figures show a strong positive relationships between BMI and all the eating behaviours subscales.

Figure 2. Relationship between BMI and Cognitive Restraint

Figure 3. Relationship between BMI and Emotional Eating

Figure 4. Relationship between BMI and Uncontrolled Eating

Relationship between BMI and eating behaviors splitting the population by their BMI

Table (5) shows that there is a significant negative relationship between BMI and Uncontrolled Eating in Obese people group ($r = -0.291^*$). The results also showed that there were no significant relationships between BMI and cognitive restraint and emotional eating when the population splitted by their BMI.

Table 5 Relationships between BMI and Eating Behaviors Splitting the Population by BMI

Eating Behaviors	BMI			
	Under weight (n=51)	Normal weight (n=216)	Over weight (n=72)	Obese (n=54)
Cognitive Restraint	r= 0.256 P= 0.069	r= 0.073 P = 0.289	r= - 0.022 P= 0.852	r = -0.161 P= 0.244
Emotional Eating	r= 0.071 P= 0.623	r= 0.089 P = 0.192	r= 0.151 P=0.204	r = - 0.102 P = 0.462
Uncontrolled Eating	r= 0.033 P= 0.817	r = 0.118 P = 0.084	r= - 0.003 P= 0.978	r = - 0.291* P= 0.033

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

The purpose of the current study was to study the eating behaviors of secondary school students in Benghazi. The study also examines the relationships between age, BMI, and eating behaviors and also identifies the influence of sex on these relationships. The TFEQ-R18 was used to study 393 students. Anthropometric measurements were measured, and BMI was calculated. For the statistical analysis, Pearson correlation was applied to measure the strength and direction of association between the age and each of the three factors CR, EE, and UE and between the BMI and each of the three factors CR, EE, and UE. The main findings are no relationships between age and eating behaviors in our population. The study also found a strong positive relationship between BMI and eating behaviors in females only and a strong negative relationship between BMI and uncontrolled eating in the obese people group.

Age, BMI, TFEQ-R18 Subscale

Results of this study showed that mean scores for BMI and the three subscales of the TFEQ-R18 were consistent with values previously reported (Zavattari, et al., 2011) (Table 1). In the present study, the results shows that there are no different in BMI and eating behaviors score between males and females, this agreed with previous studies which showed approximately equal mean scores for uncontrolled eating (Cappelleri, et al., 2009; Lluch, et al., 2000). On the other hand, earlier study that found that, cognitive restraint and emotional eating were higher among females, while uncontrolled eating was higher among males (de Lauzon, et al., 2004). Kowalkowska *et al* stated that although females usually have higher body weight concern and can be more susceptible to limit food consumption to control their weight, they are also more prone to eating in response to stress and negative emotions (de Lauzon, et al., 2004). Bryant *ea al* proposes that men seem to be more likely to consuming large amounts of food, which may be due to food palatability, hunger, and social cues (Kowalkowska, & Poínhos, 2021). Similar sex differences in the scores of TFEQ subscales were found among French adolescents and adults, except for the scores of uncontrolled eating in middle-aged adults (Bryant, et al., 2019) Higher scores of emotional eating and cognitive restraint among female students were also found in Portugal (Poínhos, et al., 2015). A study

conducted among Lebanese and Chilean students also found that females scored higher on emotional eating (Aoun, et al., 2019; Valladares, et al., 2016). In addition, research carried out among German adults revealed that females recorded higher on all three eating behavior dimensions (TFEQ subscales) (Pigeyre, et al., 2016). This dissimilarity in results between this study and previous research may be due to the different in populations, may be because this study population was younger than other population.

Association between age and Eating Behaviors

Interestingly, no significant association between eating behavior and age was found in the current study. This research was conducted among secondary school students, and the participants age was very close which it is may be the cause for no relationship between age and eating behavior in this population Abdella et al. (2019) found a negative relationship between age and eating behavior, which is may due to the population included in this study younger than previous study. In addition, Abdella *et al* in 2023 found negative significant relationship between age and cognitive restraint and emotional eating, the study was conducted on university students and staff with different age groups (Abdella, et al., 2023). Some other studies confirmed significant associations between some of the eating behavior dimensions and age. Age was positively associated with cognitive restraint and negatively connected with both disinhibition and hunger among female students satisfied with their weight (Bond, et al., 2001). Equally, a positive relationship between age with cognitive restraint and negative relationships between both uncontrolled eating and emotional eating were observed among adult males and females in Germany (Löffler, et al., 2017). Age was negatively associated with uncontrolled eating only among male students in Lebanon (Aoun, et al., 2019).

Association between BMI and Eating Behaviors

The results shows that there is a positive significant relationship between BMI and cognitive restraint and between BMI and emotional eating for the whole sample. However, when exploring the differences between males and females the result shows that in females there is a positive significant relationship between BMI all eating behaviors dimensions, while there were no relationships between BMI and eating behaviors in males. Similar to the current findings, a study confirmed a positive association between BMI and cognitive restraint and between emotional eating and BMI only between females, however, the study found no significant association between uncontrolled eating and BMI (Lluch, et al., 2000). In contrast, Cognitive restraint has been positively associated with BMI among adult males and females in Germany (Löffler, et al., 2017). Another study found that BMI was positively associated with both uncontrolled eating and emotional eating among female students in Lebanon, while, among males, with emotional eating only (Aoun, et al., 2019).

Finding of this study showed a significant negative relationship between BMI and Uncontrolled Eating in Obese people group when the population splited according to their BMI. One explanation for this result may when people weight's increase, they try to controlled in their eating and uncontrolled eating score decreased. Other study found an association between cognitive restraint and BMI when population were splited by their BMI. In France, adults with obesity presented higher cognitive restraint (Pigeyre, et al., 2016), however, in Poland, no difference between women with normal weight and those with obesity was found (Brytek-Matera, Rogoza, & Czepczor-Bernat, 2017).

The direction of the association between cognitive restraint and BMI may be different depending on the population studied, although those relations were weak, in a clinical sample of adults with obesity, cognitive restraint was inversely associated with BMI, while in a web-based survey among US adults, the association was positive (Cappelleri, et al., 2009). Likewise, another study found significant positive correlations between cognitive restraint and BMI among non-overweight (BMI

< 25 kg/m²) males and females, although they were negative between overweight (BMI _ 25 kg/m²) males and females. These results propose that adults with higher BMI demonstrated higher cognitive restraint only within a certain range of body weight status (Lowe, & Levine, 2005). On the other hand, cognitive restraint may have a counterproductive effect and lead to weight gain, since unsuccessful dieters can present high cognitive restraint and overeating tendencies (Van Strien, 2018). Cognitive restraint has been indirectly associated with body size through its interaction with disinhibition (Dykes, et al., 2004).

Conclusion

In summary, our findings indicate that no relationships between age and eating behaviors in our population, school students age may be close and no different between them. The study also found a strong positive relationship between BMI and eating behaviors in females only. The data also showed a strong negative relationship between BMI and uncontrolled eating in obese people group. These findings could open a new outline when designing plans for obesity prevention in communities, which according to our results, should consider that BMI, sex and eating behaviors as Important factors in body weight and obesity.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors have declared that, no conflict of interest.

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